

Manure Acidification and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

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ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Introduction

Agricultural activities, encompassing both crop and livestock sectors, contribute significantly to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, accounting for approximately 10 to 14% globally and around 10% in the United States (EPA, 2023b). Within the livestock sector, considerable emissions arise from manure management systems contributing 9.1% of methane (CH₄) emissions from anthropogenic sources in the U.S. (EPA, 2023b), with CH₄ emissions from manure management increasing 69% from 1990 to 2021, notably driven by a shift towards liquid manure systems, particularly from dairy cows, Figure 1 (EPA, 2023b). Methane from manure systems has a key role to play in mitigating climate change as it has a short life in the atmosphere. Given that CH₄ from manure comes from non-fossil sources, any reductions of manure CH₄ reduces global warming in the short term as CH₄ is converted to biotic carbon dioxide (CO₂). Reductions in CO₂ emissions from fossil energy systems have a stabilizing effect due to the length of time that CO₂ remains in the atmosphere (up to 1,000 years), making a strong case for investments in manure CH₄ reductions.

A similar trend is observed for nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from manure management, predominantly from manure storage which have risen from 12.4 to 17.4 MMT CO₂-eq from 1990 to 2021 and account for 3% of agricultural emissions (EPA, 2023b). However, N₂O emissions post-land application are often not fully accounted for in governmental agricultural reports under the manure management category and therefore may understate the true contributions of manure management to GHG emissions. Additionally, nearly 60% of NH₃ emissions, originating from both anthropogenic and natural sources, stem from manure management (*2017 National Emissions Inventory (NEI) Data*, 2021), impacting air quality and human health. Volatilized NH₃ can further exacerbate GHG emissions by transforming into N₂O (Hristov et al., 2009), while also reducing the nutrient content of applied manure reducing system efficiency.

When examining the combined GHG emissions from CH₄ and N₂O from manure management in the U.S., the primary emissions for targeted reduction include dairy and swine populations where the magnitude in these production systems compared to others highlights the need for mitigation. Further, when examining dairy and swine production systems, the largest number of animals in high density livestock producing states have manure management practices that include liquid/slurry storage systems. Manure acidification can reduce GHG and NH₃ emission losses and retain valuable nutrients in manure for crop production. Retaining nitrogen has the added benefit of reducing supplemental fertilizer need and the associated inputs and environmental impacts to produce them.

Figure 1. Methane (top), nitrous oxide (middle), and combined (bottom) emissions from manure management in the U.S. from 1990-2022 (EPA, 2023a)

Manure acidification involves treating manure with acids like sulfuric, phosphoric, nitric, citric, or acetic acid to lower its pH commonly in the range of 5.5 to 6.5 (David Fangueiro et al., 2015). The reduction in pH then reduces the CH₄ and NH₃ emissions losses. Lower pH levels are thought to inhibit methanogens through a variety of processes including growth and activity inhibition of *Methanosarcina* species (Habtewold, Gordon, Voroney, et al., 2018). A review by Ambrose et al. (2023) suggests additional pathways can also mitigate CH₄ production through increased organic acids (protonated VFAs) and free H₂S, consumption of H₂, and inhibitory H₂S formation, however additional work would be useful in further refining the mitigative effect of these pathways. Acidification was first evaluated to reduce NH₃ emission from manure storage. Ammonia emissions are pH dependent, where a decrease in pH shifts the NH₄⁺/NH₃ partitioning equilibrium to favor NH₄⁺ thus reducing NH₃ emissions.

Manure acidification generally involves mixing acid into manure in storage tanks or lagoons, however there are many ways to integrate the practice into livestock systems. Four primary livestock manure acidification strategies include high- and low-dose acidification in manure storage systems, acidifying manure storage inoculum (e.g. solids or manure remaining in a storage system after emptying), and acidifying manure prior to land application. Acidifying inoculum has the intention of reducing methanogen growth and activity as fresh manure is added to the system thus reducing CH₄ production (Sokolov et al., 2020). Manure acidification strategies can be implemented in-house, in-storage, or in-field (Ambrose et al., 2023; FOGED et al., 2017). In-house acidification involves treating a portion of the manure in a tank located outside the animal housing with acid and then recirculating the treated manure generally to an underbarn manure storage to acidify the larger volume of manure. This practice can also be used in flushing channels where the acidified manure is introduced in the flushing of the manure channels during cleaning. In-storage acidification is a straightforward system where acid is added directly to the manure storage and then mixed to achieve uniform distribution. Further acid can be added to manure prior to or during land applications to reduce emissions, primarily NH₃, following land application.

After acidifying manure in a storage system, the pH will increase over time due to the buffering capacity of manure with fresh manure additions to storage. Additional acidification may be needed to maintain the target pH over time, however there is limited information available to make recommendations on frequency of acid application. Further, while it is possible to acidify manure throughout the year, alternative strategies are often implemented to target periods with high emissions fluxes, with an emphasis on warmer periods when emissions tend to be the highest (Ma et al., 2022).

To date, manure acidification has been implemented at commercial farms primarily in Denmark. Case et al. (2017) identified that 19% of surveyed farmers currently used processed manures, with 10% using acidified slurry specifically, with the Danish Agricultural Agency reporting 20% of all slurry is acidified in a more recent assessment (Agency). Adoption in Denmark has been supported by stringent environmental regulations targeting reduction in NH₃ emissions and more recently a carbon tax policy encouraging acidification for CH₄ reduction from swine manure systems (Green, 2024). Other European countries, such as Germany, Sweden, and Lithuania, have also implemented acidification but the practice is less common in comparison to Denmark and often limited to research settings or pilot projects. A recent Swedish study that surveyed 99 farmers between 2021 and 2022 found that no farms currently used manure acidification (Lima et al., 2024). Manure acidification in North America has been limited to a number of research scale studies with one ongoing in Idaho and a number of publications out of Canada (Sokolov et al., 2020; Sokolov et al., 2019; Sokolov et al., 2021).

Methodology

A systematic literature review was conducted to assess farmer adoption, perceptions and policy components related to manure acidification in December 2024. The search process was conducted in both Agricola and Web of Science. The following search terms were used: “manure acidification” AND farmer; “manure acidification” AND adopt*, “manure acidification” AND perception, “manure acidification” AND policy, “manure acidification” AND cost, “slurry acidification” AND farmer, “slurry acidification” AND adopt*, “slurry acidification” AND perception, “slurry acidification” AND policy, “slurry acidification” and cost. A review of articles that included aspects specifically related to adoption, perceptions, policy or cost aspects of manure acidification yielded 17 articles for full review. In addition, other articles were obtained through cross reference of the reference lists of these articles.

A literature review of the technical performance of manure acidification regarding GHG emission mitigation was completed using Agricola with the search terms “manure” AND “acidification” AND “storage”. This returned 99 articles in 2024, of which 30 were relevant to the topic and provided details on mitigating GHG emissions from manure storage systems using acidification practices. An additional nine papers were identified cascading from this original research list. A recent review by Ambrose et al. (2023) has a detailed review of livestock manure acidification in which recent papers were reviewed to assess the scale (laboratory or pilot/farm), animal species, duration of experiment, pH range, temperature, and CH₄ mitigation. Details from this paper were expanded and reformatted for further analysis, supplementary Table S1. Median temperatures were reported for studies with temperature variations. Further, a value of zero was reported for any study that did not reduce emissions (even if there was an increase). Results from this process were then analyzed using SAS version 9.4 and used to assess the impact of manure acidification to CH₄ emissions as well as the existing gaps and general conclusions that can be drawn from current published literature.

Emissions Mitigation

Manure acidification systems primarily target mitigation of emissions from manure storage systems. The reduction in emissions is related to achieving a reduced pH that reduces the growth and activity of microorganisms contained within manure. Thus, for CH₄, methanogens are less active and produce lower amounts of CH₄ from storage systems. Achieving a reduction in CH₄ is highly dependent upon the final pH of the manure after adding acid, Figures 2-4 (Ambrose et al., 2023; Berg et al., 2006; Dalby et al., 2022; Fuchs et al., 2021; Habtewold, Gordon, Sokolov, et al., 2018; Im et al., 2021; Im et al., 2020; Kavanagh et al., 2019; Lemes et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2022; Misselbrook et al., 2016; Olafsdottir et al., 2023; Ottosen et al., 2009; Overmeyer et al., 2023; Owusu-Twum et al., 2017; Petersen et al., 2012; Petersen et al., 2014; Prado et al., 2020; Shin et al., 2019; Sokolov et al., 2020; Sokolov et al., 2019; Sokolov et al., 2021; Sommer et al., 2017; Vechi et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2023). Emissions reductions among existing studies have high agreement in performance, where the emissions mitigation is highly dependent upon the pH of the manure after acidification, where the lower the pH the greater the emissions mitigation. This is true for both CH₄ and NH₃.

Examining data from the literature review, the average reduction in emissions is statistically significant from the four pH ranges investigated of <=5.5, 5.6 to 6.0, 6.1 to 6.5, and >6.5, Figure 2, although all pH reductions resulted in an average reduction in CH₄ emissions across studies. It should be noted however,

that CH₄ emissions mitigation in almost all research is calculated as the percent reduction from a manure control that did not receive acid. This is important as the environmental conditions can greatly impact this difference based on the magnitude of the control comparison. For example, higher ambient temperatures produce higher emissions from the control can result in a larger emissions mitigation from acidification (Im et al., 2020; Overmeyer et al., 2023). Thus, in some cases where lower emissions were reported it may have been due to low emissions from the manure control.

Figure 2: Average methane emissions mitigation for all data, differing letters indicate statistically significant differences

Lab studies performed similarly to pilot or farm scale studies regarding CH₄ emissions, Figure 3, with similar trends of increasing mitigation with lower pH. At the lowest pH range (<=5.5) pilot scale studies had a slightly lower average CH₄ reduction than lab-scale studies (81% vs 90%, respectively), but could generally maintain over a 60% reduction from the control in all trials. All pilot/farm scale studies used H₂SO₄ whereas laboratory studies used a variety of acids. Researchers conducting pilot scale studies emphasized the importance of mixing to evenly distribute acid in pilot-scale studies, noting that uniformity is harder to achieve in larger systems which may account for the reduction in average performance. There are operational challenges that require integrating and mixing the acid effectively to achieve the target pH uniformly throughout the manure storage system. However, it seems many farms in Denmark have been able to integrate designs to achieve pH uniformity in acidified manure systems.

Figure 3. Methane emission mitigation by pH range in all studies (top, 103 data points over 25 studies), lab studies (middle, 77 data points over 15 studies), and pilot/farm scale studies (bottom, 26 data points over 12 studies).

Figure 4: Regression of methane emission reductions from acidified manure by pH for all studies

While the CH₄ mitigation potential for this system is consistent compared to other manure mitigation techniques, there are limited studies used to assess emissions mitigation and the many critical parameters required to achieve CH₄ mitigation. First, an effective dosage of acid to reach the desired pH is necessary. Acid rates for sulfuric acid range from 6 to 14 kg H₂SO₄ per tonne of manure across a range of studies as reported by Ambrose et al. (2023) to achieve a pH of 5.5. A barn study reported higher requirements of 17 kg H₂SO₄ (95%) per tonne of manure during the fattening stage (Overmeyer et al., 2023). This can vary based on the manure characteristics (e.g., buffering capacity) as well as the type and amount of acid used, Figure 5. Sulfuric acid is the most used acid in these systems, however other acids have been assessed in literature, namely nitric, citric, lactic, phosphoric, hydrochloric, and acetic acids. In a study by Dalby et al. (2022) where acid was added to achieve a pH of 5.5, hydrochloric, acetic, and lactic acid were still effective but had a reduced impact to that of sulfuric, nitric, and phosphoric. A review in 2015 (David Fanguero et al., 2015) indicates that sulfuric had greater reduction in NH₃ emissions from in-house systems than nitric, but the opposite was true for N₂O in the field. While the data in Figure 5 shows some low performance with sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), this is more likely due to the large number of studies using this acid compared to the studies examining other acids, Table 1. For example, lactic acid has only been evaluated in four studies, of which one had several higher pH trials that did not result in a reduction in CH₄, however if you examine only the data points with a pH ≤ 5.5 the average reduction would be 86% (Berg et al., 2006; Dalby et al., 2022; Fuchs et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023). Further, while the acids may achieve similar reductions in CH₄ emissions, the amount and cost of the acids can vary significantly.

Figure 5: Methane emission mitigation in published studies at the laboratory scale using varying acid types, all lab data (top), and only lab data that had a pH of 5.5 or less (bottom)

Table 1: Number of data points for lab studies examining manure acidification by acid type

Acid	Data points	Lab Studies
Acetic	5	3
Alum	2	1
Citric	5	1
Sulfuric (H ₂ SO ₄)	47	12
Phosphoric (H ₃ PO ₄)	2	2
Hydrochloric (HCl)	4	3
Nitric (HNO ₃)	5	3
Lactic	7	4

To maintain emissions mitigation the pH of the manure must remain in the target range, given that emissions increase with pH increases (Sommer et al. 2017). As fresh manure is added to the system and the acid is buffered, the pH decreases over time. In some cases, reacidifying is recommended, however there is little information to document when the re-acidification should take place. Further, reacidification would likely depend on the goals of the farm and the manure system design and operation. As mentioned previously, it may be most efficient to add acid in the summer months when temperatures increase emissions providing the greatest mitigative effect. However, in some cases an emissions target may warrant acidification throughout the year.

In addition to reducing CH₄ emissions, acidifying manure also has potential to reduce NH₃ emissions. In pilot/farm scale studies, NH₃ emissions reduction percentages ranged from 22% to 78%, and were generally lower than CH₄ emissions reductions (Ma et al., 2022; Misselbrook et al., 2016; Petersen et al., 2014; Sokolov et al., 2020; Sokolov et al., 2019; Sommer et al., 2017). A review of literature highlighted a range of 56% to 99% in NH₃ reductions when adding sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) to obtain a pH of 5.5 (Fuchs et al., 2021). Lemes et al. (2022) measured a lower performance in NH₃ mitigation of 8% in dairy manure NH₃ emissions mitigation in a pilot study. However, the lower reductions were likely due to the low emissions from the control due to crust formation, again indicating the control conditions have a significant impact when reporting NH₃ emission reduction percentages similar to CH₄. Misselbrook et al. (2016) reported cumulative reduction of NH₃ of 75% but also expressed emissions reductions as a percent of initial total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN) of 56, 99%, and 68% for acidified manure at an average temperature of 7, 11, and 17 degrees Celsius. Thus, highlighting the importance of temperature and mitigation metrics used for reporting. In a pilot study, Wang et al. (2014) highlighted the importance of pH in NH₃ mitigation where a 40% reduction of NH₃ emissions was reported at a pH of 5.5 but no reduction was measured at a pH of 6.5. A more recent study highlighted the relationship of pH to NH₃ emissions indicating a linear relationship, where NH₃ emissions (kg m⁻³) = pH*0.3286-1.5875 (r²=0.982) (Wang et al., 2023). Data indicate NH₃ losses via manure storage are estimated to be 35% to 44% (Liu et al., 2012), ranging from 5% to 99% depending upon the type of storage (Rotz, 2004). Integrating manure acidification can greatly reduce these losses, however to maintain this nitrogen until it reaches the plant, additional practices should be integrated in land application (e.g., manure injection and incorporation) to ensure the nitrogen is available to the plants and not lost as NH₃ following application (Aguirre-Villegas et al., 2024; Webb et al., 2010). It is likely that without the use of these practices there will be some NH₃ lost during application. If the pH remains low until land application, nitrogen losses can be mitigated, but this will require ensuring the manure is still acidified upon application.

One concern of manure acidification is the production and release of H₂S, particularly when using sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), as H₂S is a gas that has human and animal health concerns. Studies have varied reports of H₂S flux where some report significant increases in emissions (Fuchs et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2014) and others report no difference to controls (Wang et al., 2014). Overmeyer et al. (2023) found negligible amounts of H₂S (0.02 ppm) in a swine barn with acidified manure when acid was added outside the barn. Additional research is needed to understand the circumstances that may lead to increased H₂S emissions to avoid health concerns. In a pilot study, Wang et al. (2014) measured H₂S in addition to NH₃ and CH₄ and noted an increase in H₂S at a pH of 5.5 but no difference at 6.5, indicating emissions of H₂S are also pH dependent.

Practice Implementation and Adoption

Existing literature exploring manure acidification implementation is limited, where most of the peer-reviewed articles are from Europe or China. Evaluated aspects include farmer perceptions and adoption of the practice, tradeoffs in implementation, and cost and policy considerations. Extrapolation of human dimensions of practice implementation to other regions, including the United States, should be used with caution due to differing agricultural production systems, history, and policy structures. Nevertheless, several key themes emerging in the literature, including farmer's perceived benefits/drivers and barriers for adoption, tradeoff benefits and challenges, likelihood for future adoption, as well as policy implications for the practice. Each of these is described in further detail below.

Perceived Benefits, Barriers and Tradeoffs

Farmers perceived a variety of potential benefits from manure acidification, many of which were suggested or shown to positively affect adoption of the practice. First, farmers noted several agronomic benefits from the practice, including its potential for improved soil structure (Case et al., 2017), as well as the ability to increase fertilizer nitrogen (Hou et al. 2018), and potential benefits to air quality in barns (Jensen, 2002). Some studies have indicated that manure acidification can be as effective as slurry injection in reducing NH₃ emissions and could serve as a viable alternative to injection (Langley-Randall et al., 2024). Compared to other manure management strategies, acidification has a relatively low cost and cost effectiveness (Case et al., 2017; McIlroy et al., 2019; Pexas et al., 2020). Farmers also acknowledged that acidification has other environmental benefits, including its potential for reducing NH₃ emissions (Hou et al., 2018). In some regions, especially Denmark, where slurry acidification was one of the obligatory options for NH₃ mitigation, farmers identified that this policy was a key driver for technology adoption (Hou et al., 2018). A study of 129 German farmers indicated that they valued the amount of NH₃ reduction, cost share, and potential to reduce other regulatory requirements (e.g. avoiding incorporating manure during land application and covering manure storage) (Thiermann & Latacz-Lohmann, 2022).

Barriers to adopting the practice varied but included economic factors such as lack of investment capital, processing costs, and long payback periods (Hou et al., 2018), as well as unpleasant odors, nutrient content uncertainty, and planning difficulty (Case et al., 2017). Farmers perceived that the practice was less applicable to smaller livestock farms, due to less labor available (Hou et al., 2018), which aligns with findings from Case et al. (2015) where larger farms were more likely to currently use processed manures

including acidification. Farmers expressed little concern for noise, transport, and health related issues as barriers to adoption (Hou et al., 2018)

Detailed economic assessments on the costs of implementing acidification demonstrate it has good potential for reducing some environmental challenges (especially NH₃ emissions, acidification, and eutrophication potential, but is not economically beneficial for reducing GHG emissions, and studies make a variety of assumptions of varying economic inputs and costs). Pexas et al. (2020) found that slurry acidification was the most cost-effective strategy among four pig housing and three manure strategies (digestion, acidification and slurry separation) for reducing acidification and eutrophication potential in water systems. However, acidification had the lowest whole farm annual equivalent values and had high up-front costs and the lowest whole farm rate of return, and cost estimates in this study did not consider additional labor requirements. McIlroy et al. (2019) also found that acidification offered the greatest potential for cost effectively reducing NH₃ emissions. Other studies identified ways to minimize costs or provide additional value with the practice. For example, D. Fanguero et al. (2015) found that there was more intense nitrogen mineralization in acidified slurry, which could lead to higher plant available nitrogen and potentially higher crop yields, while Neerackal et al. (2017) found that operating a closed loop flush system resulted in significant cost reductions by having to apply lower acid dosages, which had the added benefit of also lowering safety and hazard concerns.

In addition to economic tradeoffs, studies also identified several other potential tradeoffs relevant to farmer implementation. First, life cycle assessments of the practice are variable on its potential to reduce GHG emissions, despite its benefits for reducing other resource concerns (Pexas et al., 2020). Relatedly, one study (Beyers et al., 2022) also suggested that slurry acidification may have more harmful impacts in categories related to the provision of energy (e.g., fossil resource depletion) or manufacturing (e.g., human toxicity). Volatile compounds formed during slurry acidification could have negative impacts on animal health, the environment and humans (Santonja et al., 2017; Saue & Tamm, 2018), though McIlroy et al. (2019) found that a slurry pH of 6 can reduce NH₃ emissions and with such a mild acidity level, there were no post animal welfare or farmworker health and safety concerns. Nevertheless, they contend that the fate of acidifiers when land applied and their effect on soil biogeochemical processes was largely unknown. Finally, D. Fanguero et al. (2015) found that there was a delay of nitrification in soils amended with acidified slurries, and acidification could affect phosphorus availability in the soil.

Future Adoption

Only a few of the available studies surveyed farmers and their potential future adoption of manure acidification, all in Europe. In a 2015 survey (Case et al., 2017), 35% of surveyed farmers indicated future interest in using processed manures, and younger farmers were significantly more likely to want to use these manures in the future. Seemingly, future adoption is variable by country driven by varying policy approaches, as Hou et al. (2018) found that while nearly 50% of Denmark respondents felt that acidification had the most potential to be applied in their country, less than 10% of respondents in Netherlands, Spain, and Italy felt this way (note: respondents were stakeholders engaged in manure treatment including farmers, farmer organization members, agricultural advisors, researchers, industry providers, and employees of public authorities). Lima et al. (2024) also surveyed Swedish farmers finding similar results, with only 7% indicating interest in using acidification in the next five years. No studies were found that examined farmer likely adoption of the practice in the United States.

Policy Design and Implementation

Several reviewed studies also discussed the policy environments and implications for manure acidification. First, several studies highlighted the regionality of the approach, and that the efficacy of manure acidification is dependent on local environmental, geography, and regulatory conditions (Beyers et al., 2022; Pexas et al., 2020). For example, the Danish regulations requiring NH₃ mitigation (and acidification as one of the available options), was a clear policy driver of adoption and adoption may remain marginal in regions that have low regulatory pressure (Hou et al., 2018). Furthermore, some assessments have also identified that slurry acidification may not be an optimal solution as compared to other strategies such as implementing stricter P application limits, which would have a larger benefit on improving environmental outcomes in the Netherlands (Beyers et al., 2022).

Facilitating the necessary policy and supply/demand environments for the adoption of manure acidification was also explored in several studies. Subsidies to assist farmers with adoption was highlighted as important to increasing the supply of acidified manures, including for the necessary capital needed to invest in long-term manure treatment, which may have significant upfront costs (Case et al., 2017; Hou et al., 2018). Other strategies to increase adoption included ensuring streamlined permit procedures for operations (Hou et al., 2018), as well as streamlining regulations for trading and transport of manures, which could also be facilitated through regional trading marketplaces (Case et al., 2017). Additional education and testing of manures for their nutrient levels would help farmers understand nutrient content as well as fertilizer values (Case et al., 2017). Given the regionality of the practice, additional regional assessment tools and analysis could provide further investigation of the geographic differences that might drive adoption efficiency and feasibility across scales (Pexas et al., 2020).

Summary

Manure acidification can reduce both CH₄ and NH₃ emissions from manure storage. Both emissions reductions are pH dependent with the highest reductions being achieved with a pH at or below 5.5. After adding acids, manure pH generally increases over time with fresh manure additions and thus requires additional acid to maintain reductions. However, an efficient mitigation technique may be targeting acidification at the start of warmer periods to reduce peak emissions. Reductions in NH₃ during storage provides a mechanism to retain nitrogen and thus reduces the quantity of supplemental nitrogen fertilizers, which farmers perceived as an added value. Barriers remain to adopting the technology including farmer education on the benefits and system operation, lack of information on various operating parameters, limited information on the impact to soil and cropping systems, and limited information on costs. Overall, there is high potential for manure acidification to be integrated into livestock farms, particularly in manure storage systems. However additional research is critical, particularly at the pilot and farm scale to further document benefits while also examining the impact of various acidification strategies and parameter optimization.

Future research is needed to evaluate system performance at both pilot and full farm scales to ensure efficacy beyond laboratory conditions. Key operational parameters, particularly acid application rates and timing, require further investigation to help potential adopters understand their practical impacts. Timing appears especially critical due to its interaction with environmental variables, notably

temperature. Identifying and promoting effective implementation strategies could significantly lower adoption barriers for livestock operations. Additionally, comprehensive research on system-wide impacts including effects on land application, greenhouse gas emissions, nutrient availability, and crop yield would provide valuable insights and strengthen the case for adoption. Engineering solutions for acid integration, including safety protocols, may also enhance outcomes while reducing input requirements. Overall, further research is essential not only to support producer decision-making but also to establish the credibility and scalability of the technology for broader agricultural stakeholders.

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Supplemental Information

Table S1. Methane emissions reductions for lab and pilot/farm scale livestock manure acidification studies, adapted from Ambrose et al. (2023)

Acid	Animal_Type	Days	Scale	pH	pH range	Temp (°C)	CH4%	Citation
Acetic acid	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	85	Dalby_2022
Acetic acid	Dairy	11	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	26	97	Fuchs_2021
Acetic acid	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	85	Fuchs_2021
Acetic acid	Dairy	84	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	8.6	63	Kavanagh_2019
Acetic acid	Dairy	85	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	8.6	87	Kavanagh_2019
Alum	Dairy	88	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	8.6	76	Kavanagh_2019
Alum	Dairy	89	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	8.6	97	Kavanagh_2019
Citric acid	Pig	35	Lab	5	<=5.5	30	99	Im_2021
Citric acid	Pig	35	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	30	99	Im_2021
Citric acid	Pig	35	Lab	6	5.6-6.0	30	92	Im_2021
Citric acid	Pig	35	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	30	0	Im_2021
Citric acid	Pig	35	Lab	7	>6.5	30	0	Im_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	14	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	99	Dalby_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	93	Dalby_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	11	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	26	88	Fuchs_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	14	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	99	Fuchs_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	93	Fuchs_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	120	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	22.5	84	Habtewold_2018
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	120	Lab	6	5.6-6.0	22.5	73	Habtewold_2018
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	120	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	22.5	43	Habtewold_2018
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	120	Pilot	6.5	6.1-6.5		69	Habtewold_2018
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	120	Pilot	5.9	5.6-6.0		84	Habtewold_2018
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	35	70	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	30	65	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	25	46	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	20	48	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	7	>6.5	35	40	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	7	>6.5	30	41	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	7	>6.5	25	29	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	43	Lab	7	>6.5	20	26	Im_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	35	Lab	5	<=5.5	30	99	Im_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	35	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	30	99	Im_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	35	Lab	6	5.6-6.0	30	87	Im_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	35	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	30	43	Im_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	35	Lab	7	>6.5	30	20	Im_2021

H ₂ SO ₄	Pig		Pilot	6.1	6.1-6.5	29	85	Im_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	86	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	8.6	69	Kavanagh_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	87	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	8.6	95	Kavanagh_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	240	Pilot	5	<=5.5	8	95	Lemes_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	240	Pilot	5	<=5.5	11.5	95	Lemes_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	63	Pilot	5.7	5.6-6.0	15	96	Ma_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	63	Pilot	5.9	5.6-6.0	15	89	Ma_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	63	Pilot	6.2	6.1-6.5	15	77	Ma_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	63	Pilot	6.3	6.1-6.5	15	66	Ma_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	63	Pilot	6.8	>6.5	15	46	Ma_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	62	Pilot	5.5	<=5.5	7	86	Misselbrrok_2016
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	71	Pilot	5.5	<=5.5	11	91	Misselbrrok_2016
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	72	Pilot	5.5	<=5.5	17	63	Misselbrrok_2016
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	78	Lab	5	<=5.5	22	100	Olafsdottir_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	78	Lab	5	<=5.5	4	100	Olafsdottir_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	78	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	22	98	Olafsdottir_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	78	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	4	96	Olafsdottir_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	78	Lab	6	5.6-6.0	22	93	Olafsdottir_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	78	Lab	6	5.6-6.0	4	80	Olafsdottir_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	0.8	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	15	99	Ottosen_2009
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	0.8	Lab	5.7	5.6-6.0	15	50	Ottosen_2009
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	60	Farm	5.5	<=5.5	16	55	Overmeyer_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	60	Farm	5.5	<=5.5	22	65	Overmeyer_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	60	Farm	5.5	<=5.5	21	80	Overmeyer_2023
H ₂ SO ₄	Cattle	40	Lab	6.41	6.1-6.5	20	0	Owusu_2017
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	20	Pilot	5.5	<=5.5	16	99	Petersen_2014
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	20	Pilot	6.5	6.1-6.5	16	94	Petersen_2014
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	62	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	27.5	86	Prado_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	40	Lab	5	<=5.5	30	97	Shin_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	40	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	30	95	Shin_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	40	Lab	6	5.6-6.0	30	89	Shin_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	40	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	30	76	Shin_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	40	Lab	7	>6.5	30	51	Shin_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	160	Pilot	6.5	6.1-6.5	16	87	Sokolov_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	160	Pilot	6	5.6-6.0	16	89	Sokolov_2019
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	155	Pilot	6	5.6-6.0	15	77	Sokolov_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	155	Pilot	6	5.6-6.0	15	38	Sokolov_2020
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	17	80	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	17	99	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	17	99	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	20	90	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	20	99	Sokolov_2021

H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	20	99	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	23	19	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	116	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	23	49	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	11	Lab	6.3	6.1-6.5	23	55	Sokolov_2021
H ₂ SO ₄	Dairy	57	Pilot	5.4	<=5.5	15.5	68	Sommer_2017
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	360	Fam	5.5	<=5.5	11.5	90	Vechi_2022
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	95	Pilot	6.5	6.1-6.5	28.5	31	Wang_2014
H ₂ SO ₄	Pig	95	Pilot	5.5	<=5.5	28.5	81	Wang_2014
H ₃ PO ₄	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	95	Dalby_2022
H ₃ PO ₄	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	95	Fuchs_2021
HCl	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	80	Dalby_2022
HCl	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	80	Fuchs_2021
HCl	Dairy	95	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	20	81	Petersen_2012
HCl	Dairy	95	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	20	66	Petersen_2012
HNO ₃	Dairy	92	Lab	4.3	<=5.5	16	75	Berg_2006
HNO ₃	Pig	14	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	99	Dalby_2022
HNO ₃	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	99	Dalby_2022
HNO ₃	Pig	14	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	99	Fuchs_2021
HNO ₃	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	99	Fuchs_2021
Lactic acid	Dairy	190	Lab	4.3	<=5.5	16	90	Berg_2006
Lactic acid	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	77	Dalby_2022
Lactic acid	Pig	18	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	23	77	Fuchs_2021
Lactic acid	Pig	43	Lab	5.5	<=5.5	27	98	Wang_2023
Lactic acid	Pig	43	Lab	6.0	5.6-6.0	27	0	Wang_2023
Lactic acid	Pig	43	Lab	6.5	6.1-6.5	27	0	Wang_2023
Lactic acid	Pig	43	Lab	7.0	>6.5	27	0	Wang_2023

Appendix: Science Gaps and Recommendations

Critical science gaps need to be filled to improve GHG mitigation research, data collection, and modeling tools to better understand the potential of conservation agriculture practices to mitigate agricultural GHG emissions within and across agricultural sectors. The gaps and needs identified below and associated recommendations are oriented to achieving the goal of enabling GHG mitigation assessment capabilities at the granularity necessary to meaningfully guide agricultural practice adoption and implementation decisions to optimize GHG mitigation across a range of geographic and operational settings. Such assessment capabilities would inform and improve the development and refinement of

public and private sector practice standards, policies, programs, and investments to incentivize practices to optimize achievement of GHG mitigation alongside profitability for farmers, cost-effectiveness for incentive and cost-share programs, and achievement of other conservation objectives.

- Existing literature exploring manure acidification implementation is limited, where most of the peer-reviewed articles are from Europe or China. Evaluated aspects include farmer perceptions and adoption of the practice, tradeoffs in implementation, and cost and policy considerations. Extrapolation of human dimensions of practice implementation to other regions, including the United States, should be used with caution due to differing agricultural production systems, history, and policy structures. Further research priorities are enumerated below.
 - Further studies focused on application in the United States are needed, including examination of farmer likelihood for adoption of acidification practices and implementation under different state and federal policy regimes. Previous studies have shown that outcomes can be related to variance across geographies, therefore further investigation in the US is required.
- Additional research on the impact to CH₄, N₂O, and NH₃ in field scale studies would greatly improve understanding of impacts. Further, evaluation of the duration of mitigation following acidification including evaluation to optimize strategies of re-acidifying.
- Additional studies are also needed to assess impacts to land application and cropping systems following manure acidification including impacts to nutrient cycling and availability.
 - Additional research to further refine the mitigative effect on CH₄ of alternative pathways such as increased organic acids (protonated VFAs) and free H₂S, consumption of H₂, and inhibitory H₂S formation.
 - Further work investigating the use of different acids in the practice of manure acidification.